

HiDyVe

Highly Dynamic Virtual and
Hybrid Validation and Verification

WP220

Transport Scenario Analysis

University of Bremen – TZI

Technical Report

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Management Summary

This technical report summarises the analysis results performed within project HiDyVe for three application scenarios from the transportations domain. The scenarios are (a) formation flight, (b) Automatic Taxiing, Take-off, and Landing (ATTOL), and (c) autonomous taxi drones that can also operate as road vehicles. The application scenarios had been defined by consortium leader Airbus before project start. Each of these scenarios represents a promising business case, provided that their Verification and Validation (V&V) and the associated certification can be performed within reasonable time frames and with acceptable costs. At the project's outset, it was anticipated that realising these scenarios would require new V&V methodologies and possibly updates to certification standards. During the project, the analysis of suitable V&V and certification approaches was further developed by the HiDyVe team at the University of Bremen. While formation flight appears feasible in terms of V&V and certification, the projected V&V and certification effort for ATTOL and taxi drones likely outweighs their expected ROI.

Preface

This technical report summarises the analysis results performed within project HiDyVe for three application scenarios from the transportations domain. They had been defined by consortium leader Airbus before project start. Each of these scenarios represents a promising business case, provided that their **V&V** and the associated certification efforts can be performed within reasonable time frames and with acceptable costs. It was expected at project start, however, that the realisation of these scenarios would require new verification methodology and perhaps also new editions of certification-related standards. During the project, the analysis of suitable **V&V** and certification approaches has been elaborated in more detail by the HiDyVe team at the university of Bremen.

[About this technical report](#)

To keep this report self-contained, we describe the three application scenarios again below.¹

Formation Flight

Recall that **platooning** is a technique applied to several trucks driving close to each other in a row, with the objective to save fuel or even allow some of the truck drivers to rest, while their trucks autonomously maintain their position in the platoon. **Formation flight** (Figure 1) is the avionic analogue to platooning: it allows several civil aircrafts to fly “in line”, with the objective to save fuel. Formation flight should require a minimum of pilot interventions, in the best case it would be autonomously controlled

[Formation flight](#)

¹The following description of transportation scenarios has been copied from the technical report [8].

by an avionic system similar to, or an extension of an auto pilot.

Figure 1: Formation flight.

Figure 2: Automatic Taxiing, Take-off and Landing (**ATTOL**).

ATTOL

Automatic taxiing, take-off, and landing (**ATTOL**) aims at letting an aircraft perform these activities autonomously, without requiring pilot intervention (Figure 2). **ATTOL**

Autonomous Taxi Drones/Vehicles.

The **Pop.Up** prototype has been developed by Airbus, Audi, and Italdesign (Figure 3). It features a passenger capsule which can be attached on top of an electric car chassis or underneath a drone. Without requiring the presence of a driver or pilot, passengers are transported by the autonomously controlled capsule-cum-chassis/drone over streets or through the air to reach their destination.

Fully
autonomous
passenger
transport

This concept could be extended to collaborating surface vehicles and drones (Figure 4): a communication and control center could dispatch several drones and vehicle chassis to cooperate with the objective to transport a large group of passengers from some starting point to their destinations. Passengers could arrive at the starting point with other traffic means or already in passenger capsules, but all should be transported to their destination by such capsules. Using distributed multi agent technology, the utilisation of surface vehicle chassis, drones, and capsules could be optimised according to different objectives (minimal energy consumption, fastest transport option depending on the current traffic situation, ...).

Collaborating
autonomous
vehicles

Figure 3: Taxi drones — Pop.Up concept by Audi, Airbus and Italdesign.

Figure 4: Collaboration scenario of autonomous surface vehicles and aerial vehicles.

As of today (2025), the Pop.up project has been discontinued – Audi left the consortium already in 2019, probably simultaneously with Italdesign who is owned by Audi.

The question whether **V&V** and certification would be feasible for such an interesting business case, however, still remains important from the perspective of research for assuring autonomy. Therefore, these aspects have been investigated further within project HiDyVe.

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Chapter 1

Formation Flight: Feasibility of V&V and Certification

1.1 Motivation of Design Decisions

As discussed in detail in the technical report [8], different system architectures influence the effort – sometimes even the feasibility – of V&V and certification campaigns. The following high-level architecture allows to encapsulate novel Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based functionality in a system partition that is *not* safety-critical, while the safety-critical functions can be handled with conventional methods and verified and certified based on conventional standards, such as

- RTCA DO-178C for avionic software verification,
- RTCA DO-254 / EUROCAE ED-80 for controller hardware V&V,
- ARP4754A for systems development assurance, and
- ARP4761 for safety analysis.

1.2 Design Approach

The design approach sketched here is inspired by the strict separation of Automated Train Protection (ATP) and Automated Train Operation

(ATO) to be expected in the designs of future autonomous trains [8, Section 14.2], [3].

Safety-critical core. The safety-critical core of a formation flight controller would be based on the core of an auto pilot and on the Traffic Alert and Collision Avoidance System (TCAS) system, but extend this with a **safety envelope controller**:

Definition 1 (Safety-Envelope)

The safety envelope is a fictitious three-dimensional ellipsoid calculated around the aircraft center, so that the complete aircraft is contained inside the ellipsoid, and two aircraft flying close to each other remain safe as long as their safety envelopes do not touch or intersect.

Obviously, the size, orientation, and position of the safety-envelope depends on the current Aircraft (A/C) pose (position plus orientation), its speed and its acceleration.

Definition 2 (Safety-Envelope Controller)

The safety envelope controller of each A/C participating in the formation flight continuously calculates its own safety-envelope, receives the positions and safety-envelope coordinates of other A/C, and checks whether the own A/C's envelope touches/overlaps with that of another A/C. If this is the case, the controller stops the formation flight application and switches to TCAS-based control, so that the A/C re-positioned in a safe distance from the other A/C.

Formation flight application. The formation flight application acts as an agent performing the following tasks:

- Negotiation of the *A/C*'s position within the formation flight configuration.
- If not in front of the formation: finding the position behind the preceding *A/C* that is best for fuel saving. This includes **future trajectory prediction** to avoid flight courses that will eventually lead to touching or intersecting safety-envelopes.
- Decision when to leave the formation.

Obviously, fuel-saving optimisation and trajectory prediction could benefit from the use of *AI*, for example a trained recurrent neural network performing the position control. These application aspects could *not* be certified by conventional means, but their design assurance level could be low (Design Assurance Level (*DAL*)-D), since the optimised positioning will only take place when the formation flight application is running, and the safety controller immediately stops this application should *A/C* be on a dangerous course in relation to each other.

Of course, *V&V* for the formation flight application would still have to be performed. Since suitable standards for the *AI*-based application components do not exist (or are currently not accepted in the aviation domain), a **specific safety case elaboration** would be required, as described in [8, Chapter 27]. The effort for this, however would be acceptable, since only *DAL*-D assurance is required. Essentially, the safety case would have to show that the formation flight application cannot lead to hazardous situations, since this is prevented by the safety envelope controller.

Summarising, our assessment is that – with a suitable system architecture – formation flight can be realised, verified, validated and certified with the methods and standards available today. Moreover, the use of *AI* is not safety-critical in formation flight, so that dedicated safety cases can be presented for these application components with acceptable effort.

Chapter 2

ATTOL: Feasibility of V&V and Certification

Regarding **ATTOL**, we focus on automatic taxiing, since this already represents challenges questioning its feasibility and the possibility of a Return of Investment (**ROI**) that justifies the considerable **V&V** and certification effort that would be necessary.

Focus on automated taxiing

2.1 Automatic Taxiing: Infeasibility of Simplistic Approach Based on Autonomous Road Vehicles

From the cost perspective, it would be most efficient to use existing technology from the automotive road vehicles domain for automated taxiing between runways and parking positions. This simplistic approach, however, will fail due to insufficient safety of the **obstacle detection**: Using existing technology for autonomous road vehicles and trains, the obstacle detection would be realised by implementing an intelligent sensor fusion from camera sensors, Light Detection and Ranging device (**LIDAR**), radar and others [2]. We have shown that with this technology and associated new **V&V** technologies (see our technical report [7]) a **hazard rate** less than 10^{-7} can be achieved [3]. This corresponds to the **tolerable hazard**

Obstacle detection can reach DAL-B, but not DAL-A

rate associated with Safety Integrity Level (SIL) 3 or DAL-B. With today's technology, however, it is unlikely that lower hazard rates can be achieved, so that a certification according to DAL-A seems infeasible.

Since collisions between aircrafts and between aircrafts and tank lorries on the taxi way could have catastrophic consequences, the obstacle detection function for automated taxiing would certainly be classified as an DAL-A application. As described above, this seems not to be feasible with existing technologies.

Automatic taxiing is DAL-A

2.2 Safe and Certifiable Approaches to Automated Taxiing

2.2.1 Solution I: Virtual Interlocking for Taxiing Routes

A certifiable solution for automatic taxiing could be “borrowed” from the railway domain:

- ‘Virtual rails’ could be introduced on airports as routes from parking positions to runways and vice versa.
- Each route would be designed in a way that an A/C taxiing on such a route would never collide with any object of the airside infrastructure (fuel hydrants and filling stations, fixed ground power units, lamp posts, maintenance or construction equipment etc.).
- Adopting the well-known technology of route-based railway interlocking [4, 6] an interlocking controller deployed in the airport would ensure that conflicting (i.e. crossing) routes that could lead to a collision of taxiing aircrafts are never allocated at the same time.
- A/C would only start taxiing when in possession of an allocated route and never deviate from the virtual rails.
- Vehicles driving on the taxi way (passenger busses, baggage transporters) must be equipped with a safety controller braking the vehicle

Virtual rails and route-based interlocking

when in danger of entering an allocated route.

In principle, this technical concept could be verified, validated, and certified with classical methods: no AI is needed in any part of this design. The costs to implement this, however, make it unlikely that a sufficient ROI would justify the approach.

2.2.2 Solution II: Utilisation of Safety Envelopes

An alternative to Solution I would be to introduce safety envelopes (see Section 1.2) not only for A/C, but also for each object of the airside infrastructure and for all ground vehicles moving on the taxi way.

- Static objects of the airside infrastructure would just broadcast the coordinates of their position and safety envelope.
- Vehicles would be additionally equipped with a safety controller that stops the vehicle when getting too close to the safety envelope of an A/C.
- When taxiing, A/C would find their way dynamically, using AI to choose optimised paths. As discussed in Section 1.2, this would not be safety-critical, since a separate safety envelope controller would stop the A/C as soon as the danger of a collision arises.

Compared to Solution I, this concept is more flexible since it does not require the design of fixed taxiing routes. It could be verified, validated, and certified in analogy to the concept described in Section 1.2. However, the costs for equipping airside infrastructure and ground vehicles with controllers broadcasting their safety envelopes and checking their movements will probably not be justified by a sufficient ROI.

CHAPTER 2. ATTOL: FEASIBILITY OF V&V AND CERTIFICATION⁷

Summarising, automated taxing, and, therefore, the whole **ATTOL** application cannot be certified according to the required safety level **DAL-A** if a cost effective adaptation of road vehicle technologies are used for obstacle detection. Sufficiently safe and certifiable solutions, on the other hand, require considerable technological changes for airports, so that a sufficient **ROI** seems unlikely. Thus we do not expect that a promising solution for **ATTOL** technology can be realised in the near future.

Chapter 3

Autonomous Taxi Drones/Vehicles: Feasibility of V&V and Certification

While first applications with autonomous taxi road vehicles have started in the USA, in China, and even in Europe (Germany¹) have been deployed during our research project HiDyVe, the complexity and the hazards presented by autonomously flying taxi drones result in a significantly higher degree of safety-criticality. This is because

- system control of an areal vehicle is more complex than that of a road vehicle,
- an accident caused by a taxi drone can result in much more severe damage than that caused by an autonomous car²,
- in contrast to formation flight of civil A/C flying in protected corridors, taxi drones could encounter many more types of flying objects³, as well as static objects⁴ that might cause collisions.

Autonomous taxi drones represent higher risks than autonomous road vehicle taxis.

¹https://www.deutschebahn.com/de/presse/pressestart_zentrales_uebersicht/Pionierprojekt-KIRA-startet-mit-autonomen-Fahrzeugen-fuer-den-OePNV--12926526?utm_source=chatgpt.com

²e.g. a crash into a densely populated area or critical infrastructure such as a hospital

³from birds, kites and small “toy drones” to helicopters

⁴buildings, power lines, lamp posts, . . .

Consequently, the collision detection mechanism of taxi drones would certainly be classified as DAL-A. As discussed in the previous chapter, current intelligent sensor fusions used for autonomous cars cannot achieve the low hazard rates ($< 10^{-9}$) required for DAL-A or SIL-4. So, again, the obstacle detection technology for road vehicles cannot simply be reused for taxi drones.

Taxi drones might be scheduled to fly on pre-defined routes⁵. This could reduce or even avoid the danger of colliding taxi drones. However, police and rescue helicopters could never be expected to fly on scheduled trajectories, so the collision risk is still high. Moreover, the safety envelope technique that would work well for formation flight is expected to be inapplicable for areal vehicles flying through cities, since the distances to other objects would be far shorter.

Even if another, currently unknown, technology promises to solve these problems, the V&V effort would certainly require so many tests that a major portion of them needs to be executed in a trustworthy cloud simulation environment. This however, requires very high effort for the qualification of simulations and execution environments (virtual prototypes), as we have discussed in [8, Chapter 19]. While this V&V effort might be compensated very well by the ROI to be expected for large fleets of road vehicle taxis, it is doubtful that the same ROI can be expected for flying taxi drones.

Summarising, our assessment shows that the V&V and certification effort for autonomous taxi drone/vehicles would be too high in comparison to the ROI to be expected.

⁵similar to the concept used in the German pilot project referenced above, where autonomous road vehicles drive along pre-defined roads with pre-defined stops

Chapter 4

Bibliography

- [1] European Union Aviation Safety Agency EASA. EASA Concept Paper: First usable guidance for Level 1 machine learning applications – A deliverable of the EASA AI Roadmap. Technical report, 2021. URL https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/easa_concept_paper_first_usable_guidance_for_level_1_machine_learning_applications_-_proposed_issue_01_1.pdf.
- [2] Francesco Flammini, Stefano Marrone, Roberto Nardone, Mauro Caporuscio, and Mirko D’Angelo. Safety integrity through self-adaptation for multi-sensor event detection: Methodology and case-study. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 112:965–981, 2020. ISSN 0167-739X. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2020.06.036>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X19333734>.
- [3] Mario Gleirscher, Anne E. Haxthausen, and Jan Peleska. Probabilistic risk assessment of an obstacle detection system for goa 4 freight trains. In *Proceedings of the 9th ACM SIGPLAN International Workshop on Formal Techniques for Safety-Critical Systems*, FTSCS 2023, page 26–36, New York, NY, USA, 2023. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9798400703980. doi: 10.1145/3623503.3623533.
- [4] Linh Vu Hong, Anne Elisabeth Haxthausen, and Jan Peleska. Formal modelling and verification of interlocking systems featuring sequential release. *Sci. Comput. Program.*, 133:91–115, 2017. doi: 10.1016/j.scico.2016.05.010. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scico.2016.05.010>.
- [5] Philip Koopman and Michael D. Wagner. Autonomous vehicle safety: An interdisciplinary challenge. *IEEE Intell. Transp. Syst. Mag.*, 9(1):90–96, 2017. doi: 10.1109/MITS.2016.2583491. URL <https://doi.org/10.1109/MITS.2016.2583491>.
- [6] Jörn Pachl. *Railway Signalling Principles*. Self-published, Braunschweig, Germany, 2021. URL <http://www.joernpachl.de/eBook%20RSP.pdf>. Accessed: 2025-06-23.

- [7] Jan Peleska, Felix Brüning, Mario Gleirscher, and Wen-ling Huang. *HiDyVe: A Stochastic Approach to Classification Error Estimates in Convolutional Neural Networks*, June 2025. URL <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.06156>. Technical report.
- [8] Jan Peleska, Felix Brüning, Mario Gleirscher, and Wen-ling Huang. *HiDyVe: Ultra Complex and Autonomous Cyber-physical Systems — State-of-the-Art Analysis*, June 2025. URL <https://zenodo.org/records/15745068>. Technical report.
- [9] The British Standards Institution (BSI), Centre for Connected & Autonomous Vehicles. PAS 1883:2020, Operational Design Domain (ODD) taxonomy for an automated driving system (ADS) – Specification, August 2022.

Appendix A

Abbreviations

A/C Aircraft

ACAS Airborne collision avoidance system

ACWG Assurance Case Working Group

ADAS Advanced Driver Assistance Systems

ADS Automated Driving System

AEB Automated Emergency Braking System

AFDX Avionics Full-Duplex Switched Ethernet

AI Artificial Intelligence

A/IS Autonomous and Intelligent Systems

ALARP As Low As Reasonably Practicable (risk management principle)

ANN Artificial Neural Network

AOP Agent-Oriented Programming

AOSE Agent-Oriented Software Engineering

ATM Air Traffic Management

ATO Automated Train Operation

ATP Automated Train Protection

ATTOL Automatic Taxiing, Take-off, and Landing

AV Autonomous Vehicle

BIP Behavior, Interaction, Priority component framework

BIST Built-In Self Test

BDI Belief-Desire Intention (for agent programming)

BITE Built-in Test Equipment

BMWi Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy

BSI British Standards Institution

CAT Commercial Air Transport (passengers, cargo, mail)

CCP Coupon Collector's Problem

CGF Coverage-Guided Greybox Fuzzing

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

CP Conformal Prediction

CPS Cyber-Physical Systems

CTMC Continuous Time Markov Chain

DAL Design Assurance Level

DDT All of the real-time operational and tactical functions required to operate a vehicle in on-road traffic (Definition taken verbatim from [9].)

DFA Deterministic finite automaton

DL Deep Learning

DNN Deep Neural Network

DOT US Department of transportation

DP Driving policy

DSL Domain Specific Language

DTMC Discrete Time Markov Chain

DUV Design Under Verification

DTF Digital Twin Framework

EAI Embodied Artificial Intelligence

EASA European Union Aviation Safety Agency

ECU Electronic Control Unit (automotive domain)

E/E system Electrical and/or electronic system

ETCS European Train Control Systems

FAA Federal Aviation Administration of the USA

FMI Functional Mock-up Interface

FMVSS Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards (USA)

FSM Finite State Machine

FT Fault Tree

GAN Generative adversarial network

GoA Grade of Automation

GSN Goal Structure Notation

GSMP Generalized Semi-Markov stochastic Process

HARA Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment

HIC Human in Command

HITL Human in the loop

HIL Hardware-in-the-Loop (testing)

HOA Hanoi Omega Automata

HRI Human Robot Interaction

HW Hardware

IA Impact Analysis

IID Independent and Identically Distributed

IMA Integrated Modular Avionics

IXL Railway Interlocking System

LBIST Logic Built-In Self Test

LIDAR Light Detection and Ranging device

LTL Linear Temporal Logic

MAPE Monitor, Analyse, Plan, Execute (execution cycle of autonomic managers)

MAS Multi-Agent System

MAV Micro Aerial Vehicles

MBSE Model-based Systems Engineering

MBT Model-based Testing

MC Markov Chain

MEM Minimal Endogenous Mortality principle: based on the idea that the introduction of a technical system should not significantly increase the death rate in society

MDP Markov Decision Process

MIL Model-in-the-Loop (testing)

ML Machine Learning

MRC minimal risk condition

NCAP New Car Assessment Programme

NHTSA National Highway Traffic Safety Administration

NN Neural Network

OE Original Equipment

OD Obstacle Detection

ODD Operational Design Domain

OGSA Open Grid Services Architecture

OMG Object Management Group

OSLC Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration

PAS A Publicly Available Specification or PAS is a standardization document that closely resembles a formal standard in structure and format but which has a different development model. The objective of a Publicly Available Specification is to speed up standardization. PASs are often produced in response to an urgent market need. (This definition has been taken verbatim from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Publicly_Available_Specification.) A PAS is co-branded with the BSI (British Standards Institution). (<https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/our-services/developing-new-standards/Develop-a-PAS/what-is-a-pas/>)

PBT Property-Based Testing

PIM Platform Independent Model

POT Property-Oriented Testing

PSM Platform Specific Model

QoS Quality of Service

RAS Robotics and Autonomous Systems

RBC Radio Block Centre

ReLU Rectified Linear Unit

REST Representational State Transfer

RNN Recurrent Neural Networks

ROI Return of Investment

RQ Research Question

SAE Society of Automotive Engineers

SCSC Safety-Critical Systems Club (see <https://scsc.uk>)

SDF Simulation/Scene Description Format

SFSM Symbolic Finite State Machine

SiL Software-in-the-Loop (testing)

SIL Safety Integrity Level

SOAP Simple Object Access Protocol

SoS Systems of Systems

SOTIF Safety of the Intended Functionality

SPL Software Product Line

SUT System Under Test

SW Software

TAS Trustworthy Autonomous Systems

TCAS Traffic Alert and Collision Avoidance System

TQ Tool Qualification

TTC Time to Collision

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

UCL Upper Confidence Limit

UKRI UK Research and Innovation

UML Unified Modelling Language

USM Utility State Machine

USP Unique Selling Point

UTM Unmanned Aircraft System Traffic Management

VBI Vehicle Behaviour Interface

VLSS Vehicle level safety strategy

VP Virtual Prototype

VRU Vulnerable Road User

V&V Verification and Validation

V2X Vehicle to Infrastructure (communication)

WCET Worst Case Execution Time

WP Work Package

WPBS Work Package Break-down Structure

XAI Explainable Artificial Intelligence

XMI XML Metadata Interchange

XML Extensible Markup Language

Appendix B

Glossary

Accident An unexpected event that causes damage, injury, or harm. See also **incident**

Adaptivity The ability to improve performance by learning from experience. [In the Machine Learning context], a system is considered adaptive when it continues to learn in real-time operation

Artificial intelligence (AI) Technology that appears to emulate human performance typically by learning, coming to its own conclusions, appearing to understand complex content, engaging in natural dialogues with people, enhancing human cognitive performance (also known as cognitive computing) or replacing people on execution of non-routine tasks. Applications include autonomous vehicles, automatic speech recognition and generation, and detection of novel concepts and abstractions (useful for detecting potential new risks and aiding humans to quickly understand very large bodies of ever-changing information)

Artificial neural network (ANN) A computational graph that consists of connected nodes ('neurons') that define the order in which operations are performed on the input. Neurons are connected by edges, which are parameterised by weights (and biases). Neurons are organised in layers, specifically an input layer, several intermediate layers, and an output layer. This document refers to a specific type of neural

network that is particularly suited to process image data: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which use parameterised convolution operations to compute their outputs. Commonly used types of neural networks are to be highlighted: **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)**, **Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)**, **Generative adversarial networks (GANs)**

Automation The use of control systems and information technologies reducing the need for human input, typically for repetitive tasks

Autonomy The ability to perform tasks in complex environments without input by a human

Avionics Electronics (including computers), as applied in aviation

Bias An error from erroneous assumptions in the learning [process]. High bias can cause an algorithm to miss the relevant relations between attributes and target outputs (=underfitting)

Big Data A new technology, which allows the analysis of big amount of data (more than terabytes), with a high velocity (high speed of data processing), from various sources (sensors, images, texts, etc.), and which might be unstructured (not standardised format)

Brittle (deep neural network) A trained DNN is called brittle if seemingly small changes in the input data lead to drastic changes in the output, resulting, for example, in an erroneous image classification

cloud-native repository A data archive residing in the cloud which can be evaluated and manipulated in the cloud as well, without the necessity to download this data to local computers

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) - a specialised kind of neural network for processing data that has a known grid-like topology. Convolutional networks use convolution [a specialised kind of linear operation] in place of general matrix multiplication in at least one of their layers

DARPA (Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency) A US Government Agency whose mission is to make pivotal investments in breakthrough technologies for national security

Data for safety (EASA) Data4Safety (also known as D4S) is a data collection and analysis programme that supports the goal of ensuring the highest common level of safety and environmental protection for the European aviation system. The programme aims at collecting and gathering all data that may support the management of safety risks at European level. This includes safety reports (or occurrences), flight data (i.e. data generated by the aircraft via the flight data recorders), surveillance data (air traffic data), weather data - but those are only a few from a much longer list. As for the analysis, the programme's ultimate goal is to help to 'know where to look' and to 'see it coming'. In other words, it will support the performance-based environment and set up a more predictive system. More specifically, the programme will facilitate better knowledge of where the risks are (safety issue identification), determine the nature of these risks (risk assessment) and verify whether the safety actions are delivering the needed level of safety (performance measurement). It aims to develop the capability to discover vulnerabilities in the system across terabytes of data

Data science A broad field that refers to the collective processes, theories, concepts, tools and technologies that enable the review, analysis and extraction of valuable knowledge and information from raw data

Data-driven AI The data-driven [approach] focuses on building a system that can [learn] what is the right answer based on having [trained on] a large number of [labelled] examples

Deep learning (DL) A specific type of machine learning based on the use of large neural networks to learn abstract representations of the input data by composing many layers

Digital twin *"A digital twin is a virtual representation that serves as the*

*real-time digital counterpart of a physical object or process.*¹

Embodied artificial intelligence (EAI) In EAI, AI algorithms learn through embodied physical interactions with their environments, whether real or simulated

Epistemologic defeaters Conditions or events leading to the loss, reduction, or prevention of some positive epistemic status, that is, conditions or events counting *against* a belief

Epistemology The study of knowledge and the justification of beliefs

Explainable AI “*is artificial intelligence (AI) in which the results of the solution can be understood by humans.*”²

Functional safety is the part of the overall safety of a system or piece of equipment that depends on automatic protection operating correctly in response to its inputs or failure in a predictable manner (fail-safe). The automatic protection system should be designed to properly handle likely human errors, systematic errors, hardware failures and operational/environmental stress.³

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) - a type of construct in neural network technology that is composed of two neural networks: a generative network and a discriminative network. These work together to provide high-level simulation of conceptual tasks

Illocutionary force The intention of the sender in a message exchanged between agents

Impact analysis (also change impact analysis) “*is the analysis of changes within a deployed product or application and their potential consequences*”.⁴

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_twin

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Explainable_artificial_intelligence

³definition adopted verbatim from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_safety

⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Change_impact_analysis

Incident Any unexpected event that does not result in serious losses or injury, but *might* have caused an accident. For formally, an incident occurs if a system reaches a hazardous state from which it recovers without entering an accident state before

Inference The process of feeding the machine learning model an input and computing its output. See also related definition of ‘Training’

Internet of things (IoT) The network of physical objects that contain embedded technology to communicate and sense or interact with their internal states or the external environment

Machine learning (ML) Rooted in statistics and mathematical optimisation, machine learning is the ability of computer systems to improve their performance by exposure to data without the need to follow explicitly programmed instructions. [Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence]. Machine learning strategies go by three methods **Supervised learning**, **Unsupervised learning** and **Reinforcement learning**

Machine learning model A parametrised function that maps inputs to outputs. The parameters are determined during the training process

minimal risk condition Vehicle state in order to reduce the risk of harm, when a given trip cannot be completed

Mode confusion The actual system state differs from what a responsible human (e.g. driver, pilot) thinks the state is (e.g. pilot thinks that auto pilot is active while it is actually switched off)

Model-driven AI Model-driven AI (or symbolic AI), instead, attempts to capture knowledge and derive decisions through explicit representation and rules

Narrow AI Artificial intelligence that is focused on one narrow task

Neural network A computational graph that consists of connected nodes ('neurons') that define the order in which operations are performed on the input. Neurons are connected by edges, which are parameterised by weights (and biases). Neurons are organised in layers, specifically an input layer, several intermediate layers, and an output layer. This document refers to a specific type of neural network that is particularly suited to process image data: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which use parameterised convolution operations to compute their outputs. Commonly used types of neural networks are to be highlighted: **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)**, **Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)**, **Generative adversarial networks (GANs)**

Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration (OSLC) is an open community creating specifications for *interactions between tools*. The objective is to facilitate the development of IDEs, including issue tracking, testing, and other services relevant for the lifecycle of software-based products. In particular, IDEs should become more flexible with the help of OSLC, so that it will become easier to integrate tools of other providers, as long as these tools conform to the data exchange protocols provided by OSLC

Operational safety means the absence of unreasonable risk under the occurrence of hazards resulting from functional insufficiencies of the intended functionality (e.g. false/missed detection), operational disturbances (e.g. environmental conditions like fog, rain, shadows, sunlight, infrastructure) or by reasonably foreseeable misuse/errors by the driver, passengers and other road users (safety hazards — without system faults).⁵

Performative same meaning as *illocutionary force*

Predictability/determinism A system is predictable/deterministic if when given identical inputs, produces identical outputs

⁵definition adopted verbatim from <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/operational-safety>

- Rebutting defeater** A defeater (in epistemology) providing evidential support for the opposite thesis of a belief
- Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)** - a type of advanced artificial neural network (ANN) that involves directed cycles in memory. One aspect of recurrent neural networks is the ability to build on earlier types of networks with fixed-size input vectors and output vectors
- Reinforcement learning** In this algorithm, the neural network is reinforced for positive results, and punished for a negative result, forcing the neural network to learn over time
- Resilience** Attribute of systems and applications to ensure high service availability through monitoring and automatic adjustment of redundant or virtualized infrastructure components
- Road furniture (also street furniture)** A collective term for objects and pieces of equipment installed along streets and roads for various purposes. It includes benches, traffic barriers, bollards, post boxes, phone boxes, streetlamps, traffic lights, traffic signs, bus stops, tram stops, taxi stands, public lavatories, fountains, watering troughs, memorials, public sculptures, and waste receptacles
- Robustness** For an input varying in a region of the state space, the system is producing the same outputs
- Safety science** A broad field that refers to the collective processes, theories, concepts, tools and technologies that support safety management
- Safing mission** A behaviour triggered when sudden events increase the risk in an unacceptable way. The objective of this behaviour is to transfer the system into a stable safe state as quickly as possible [5]
- Supervised learning** - the process of learning a function that maps an input to an output based on example input-output training samples

Training The process of optimising the parameters (weights) of a machine learning model given a data set and a task to achieve on that data set. For example, in supervised learning, the training data consists of input (e.g. an image) / output (e.g. a class label) pairs and the machine learning model 'learns' the function that maps the input to the output, by optimising its internal parameters. See also related definition of 'Inference'

Undercutting defeater A defeater (in epistemology) removing support for a belief

Unsupervised learning - this strategy is used in cases where there is no labelled data set available to learn from. The neural network analyses the data set, and then a cost function tells the neural network how far off target it was. The neural network then adjusts to increase accuracy of the algorithm

Variance An error from sensitivity to small fluctuations in the training set. High variance can cause an algorithm to model the random noise in the training data, rather than the intended outputs (=overfitting)

Vehicle to everything (V2X) communication Communication between a (potentially autonomous) vehicle and "*any entity that may affect, or may be affected by, the vehicle.*"⁶

Vulnerable Road User (VRU) A road user who is not occupying a vehicle such as a passenger car, a public transit vehicle, or a train

A part of this glossary has been adopted verbatim from [1].

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vehicle-to-everything>